

A Metamaterial Particle Exhibiting Polarization Independence for In-plane Wave Propagation: Introducing the PI-SRR

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Abstract—We propose a new metamaterial resonant particle possessing the ability to screen the electromagnetic energy at in-plane incidence regardless of the wave polarization, utilizing a fully numerical approach based on the revealing of the intrinsic behavior of the utilized resonator components via the computational solution of the corresponding eigenproblems. We begin with the combination of a typical EC-SRR particle with a metallic cylinder placed perpendicularly at its center, with respect to the resonator’s plane. This composite medium supports the superposition of the separate modes of its components, exhibiting simultaneous negative effective permittivity and permeability at the same axis, parallel to the cylinders. The substitution of the cylinder with the recently proposed simplified complementary EC-SRR leads to the fully planar version of the polarization independent SRR (PI-SRR). Subsequently, the uniplanar version of the proposed resonator is designed, based on a combination of an ordinary one-split SRR and a complementary resonator. The simulation results illustrate a very consistent behavior concerning the capability of the structures to support the electric and magnetic resonant modes almost intact, without interacting with one another, as proved by their illustrated field distributions in the proximity of the scatterers.

Index Terms—complementary split-ring resonators, Bloch-Floquet FEM Formulation, eigenvalue analysis, polarization-independence

I. INTRODUCTION

THE evolution of metamaterials during the last two decades may be reflected on the hundreds of articles published in the broader scientific field [1]–[5]. Through the utilization of several numerical, semi-analytical or analytical techniques, these composite media were thoroughly studied in terms of their electromagnetic properties: Synthesis of novel resonators exhibiting magnetic or electric resonance, effective parameter retrieval techniques, incorporation in more complex components, etc., have been proposed, initially to operate at microwave frequencies, and appropriately modified and scaled, subsequently, for operation at the THz spectrum [6]–[16]. Among the metamaterial particles, the most popular one is the split-ring resonator (SRR), initially proposed in [17], exhibiting an effective magnetic permeability of resonant type when periodically assigned in a 3D-pattern (e.g., a cubic lattice). Either in its initial edge-coupled version (EC-SRR) or in its subsequent variations [Broadside-Coupled (BC-SRR),

Non-Bianisotropic (NB-SRR), etc.] [18]–[20], designed with a varying number of splits or concentric rings, this meta-atom was studied in a plethora of applications and was integrated in several microwave components, such as waveguides, antennas, filters, dividers, etc. [21]–[23].

Soon after the realization of the effective magnetic permeability through the SRR composite periodic media, the combination of SRRs with thin wires led to the implementation of the first double-negative metamaterial, a composite which exhibits simultaneous electric and magnetic resonance at orthogonal directions [24]–[30]. Moreover, based on Babinet’s principle, the design of complementary resonators – the dual counterpart of SRRs – led to a particle, the periodic repetition of which, forms a composite medium that exhibits negative effective dielectric permittivity when repeated on a periodic lattice [31]–[41]. Initially, the design of the resonators concerned in-plane wave incidence, i.e., wave propagation with the wavevector laying at the resonators’ plane. In subsequent studies, perpendicular or oblique incidence was thoroughly explored, which led to the evolution of metasurfaces and their applications (absorbers, polarizers, etc.) [42]–[45]. At that point, the invention of electrical resonators was crucial, since they constitute the particles that exhibit electric resonance when excited by perpendicular or oblique wave incidence [46], [47].

In this work, we introduce a novel metamaterial particle that exhibits simultaneous electric and magnetic resonance in the same direction. The structure is independent of the wave polarization under in-plane incidence, whereas it is based on the combination of previously proposed resonant structures, exploiting the superposition of their supported modes. Its synthesis is totally built on a computational approach, exploiting the intrinsic behavior of the particles under study, available by the solutions returned from eigenvalue simulations; additionally, excitation (wave propagation) solutions are also utilized to confirm the capability of these structures to operate at microwave frequencies under the excitation of specifically polarized electromagnetic waves. A step-by-step procedure is followed towards the synthesis of the desired particle: Initially, we study the behavior of a composite medium consisting of the combination of an EC-SRR and a vertically placed metallic cylinder in its center. It is proved that this structure is capable of supporting both the modes of each of its separate components, therefore its periodic

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Fig. 1. (a) Unit cell of a composite medium consisting of metallic cylinders (b) Unit cell of an EC-SRR medium (c) Unit cell of a combined metallic cylinder/EC-SRR medium. The edge of the cubic lattice is $d_x = d_y = d_z = 10$ mm. The rest of the dimensions depicted are: $d = 1$ mm, $r = 3.6$ mm, $w = 0.9$ mm, $s = 0.2$ mm, $t = 0.2$ mm.

repetition constitutes a medium which exhibits negative values of effective electric and magnetic permeability in the same direction, at a prescribed frequency zone.

Subsequently, we present a fully-planar particle consisting solely of two-dimensional (printed) resonators, by substituting the vertical metallic cylinder component with the simplified complementary EC-SRR, proposed in [48]. The resulting polarization-independent SRR (PI-SRR) composite medium has the capability of screening the electromagnetic field under both orthogonal polarizations of the impinging wave at the same microwave frequency zone. As a last step, the uniplanar version of the PI-SRR is proposed, with both resonators printed on the same plane, equally supporting both separate modes, as confirmed by the illustrated field distributions and the returned dispersion diagram. The proposed particle is considered to be utilized as a visual electric and magnetic wall in microwave structures, such as the metamaterial-inspired Substrate-Integrated Waveguides and Leaky-Wave Antennas, for the minimization of the leaky-wave losses [49].

II. COMBINATION OF METALLIC CYLINDER AND SPLIT-RING RESONATOR

As thoroughly described in the literature, a medium consisting of metallic cylinders periodically arranged in a square array exhibits negative effective electric permittivity in a certain frequency range, depending on the dimensions of the cylinders, the lattice period and the filling fraction [50], [51]. Assuming the arrangement of Fig. 1(a), an electric field E_z parallel to the axis of the cylinders excites the dominant mode of this structure, producing an effective medium exhibiting negative real part of effective dielectric permittivity ($\text{Re}\{\epsilon_{rzz,\text{eff}}\} < 0$). This effect finds application at Substrate Integrated Waveguides (SIWs), where metallic vias substitute the narrow walls of a metallic orthogonal waveguide, screening an electric field polarized parallel to their axis [52]. It is noted that the described response is of a non-resonant form. On the other hand, a composite medium consisting of split-ring resonators arranged on a cubic periodic lattice exhibits negative effective magnetic permeability ($\text{Re}\{\mu_{rzz,\text{eff}}\} < 0$), under the assumption that the resonators lay on the xy plane and the incidence of an H_z magnetic field [Fig. 1(b)]. This response is due to the antiparallel magnetic polarizability created at the effective medium as a result of the splits on

Fig. 2. Dispersion diagram of the EC-SRR composite medium, k_x incidence. Eigenvalues with large propagation and attenuation constants are plotted in green color, whereas the ones with very small (tend to zero) propagation constant and large attenuation constant are plotted in red. Those which form the branches of the EC-SRR and BC-SRR modes (passband) are depicted in blue and the lightline modes are given in black color. The lightline is plotted with continuous black line.

Fig. 3. Transmission coefficients for a plane wave incident on an EC-SRR medium for varying polarization angle θ . At $\theta = 0$ (E_y, H_z, k_x) the primary in-plane response of the medium is excited, whereas at $\theta = 90^\circ$ ($E_z, -H_y, k_x$) the wave is totally transmitted (excitation of lightline mode). Intermediate angles also illustrated.

the rings, and is of resonant type, depending on the specific geometrical parameters of the resonators (ring radius, split width, etc.) [8], [17].

In this section, a composite medium combining the two aforementioned structures is proposed. In the center of each EC-SRR, a penetrating metallic cylinder is inserted, as depicted in Fig. 1(c). In this way, the superposition of the responses of the two separate media is expected: A simultaneous electric and magnetic response on the z axis at a specific frequency spectrum. Of course, it is natural to think that the interaction between the two particles has to be taken into account. For this reason, we firstly consider the behaviour of each particle separately, utilizing two full-wave numerical tools: The **E** – **B** Bloch-Floquet FEM Formulation [53]–[57] for the eigen-analysis of the unit cells of the periodic structures and the wave propagation solver of the RF Module of Comsol MultiphysicsTM for the solution of the corresponding excitation problem.

Initially, the behavior of the separate split-ring resonator composite medium is illustrated. The EC-SRR medium is described thoroughly in [8], among various SRR media. Here, we present the dispersion diagram for the case of k_x incidence in Fig. 2. It is easily observed that there is a bandgap region

Fig. 4. Dispersion diagram of a metallic cylinder medium, illustrated in Fig. 1(a). The dominant mode supported by the structure (plotted in red color), is extremely evanescent exhibiting an attenuation constant $\alpha > 250$ Np/m at the frequency range simulated. The medium supports another mode (plotted in blue) corresponding to the orthogonal (H_z) polarization with a propagation constant slightly larger than the lightline (plotted in black color).

Fig. 5. Transmission coefficients for plane wave incidence on the metallic cylinder medium of Fig. 1(a) for a varying polarization angle θ . ($E_z, -H_y, k_x$) polarization $\theta = 90^\circ$ is totally reflected whereas at $\theta = 0^\circ$ (E_y, H_z, k_x) the wave is fully transmitted, confirming the corresponding dispersion diagram of Fig. 4. Intermediate angles depicted, as well.

between 5.2 and 6 GHz due to its resonance, which corresponds to its negative effective permeability region excited by an incident H_z magnetic field. The orthogonal wave incidence (E_z) corresponds to the lightline mode: This type of wave ignores the presence of the resonators and propagates as in free space, polarized as a TEM wave exhibiting loss due to the presence of the conductive resonators. In addition, the excitation of this composite periodic medium with a TEM wave of varying field polarization is also examined. In Fig. 3, the transmission coefficients for angles between $\theta = 0^\circ$ (E_y, H_z, k_x) and $\theta = 90^\circ$ ($E_z, -H_y, k_x$) are illustrated (θ is the elevation angle), exhibiting the behavior of the structure at intermediate angles, as well. It is easily observed that for the angle cases of $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = 22.5^\circ$ there is a clear minimization of the transmittance at the frequency zone predicted by the dispersion diagram of Fig. 2, whereas the response of the medium deviates from this behavior when the angle becomes larger. At $\theta = 90^\circ$ the transmission reaches a maximum, as the field propagates as a TEM wave in free space. This wave corresponds to the supported lightline mode at the dispersion diagram).

Subsequently, a unit cell consisting of metallic cylinders located at its center is simulated. The details of the structure are illustrated in Fig. 1(a) and the returned dispersion diagram

Fig. 6. Dispersion diagram of the combined metallic cylinder/ EC-SRR medium of Fig. 1(c). Two distinct modes are returned from the FEM eigen-analysis: The SRR mode (depicted in blue) constitutes the two branch line which is identical to the separate EC-SRR medium dispersion (Fig. 2) and the cylinder's mode (red color) remains identical to the separate cylinder medium case (Fig.4).

is depicted in Fig. 4. The supported dominant mode of the structure (plotted in red color) is extremely evanescent, revealing its capability to block the incident field, due to the induced antiparallel electric polarizability. Of course, the medium supports another mode, as well (plotted in blue), which corresponds to the orthogonal wave polarization (H_z incident field). Precisely, this mode's wavenumber is slightly larger than the free space wavenumber, as seen by the comparison with the depicted lightline slope. It is easily concluded that this polarization of the incident wave does not “feel” the composite medium, rendering it indifferent to such a wave incidence. Moreover, the corresponding excitation problem is solved in this case, too, with a varying polarization angle (Fig. 5), with its results confirming the described eigenvalue analysis.

In the following subsections the combined EC-SRR/ metallic cylinder medium illustrated in Fig. 1(c) is examined. An eigenmode analysis is conducted, revealing its behavior in frequency. The supported modes are visualized depicting the field distributions at several planes inside the unit cell. In addition, the results of an excitation simulation are also presented, assuming plane wave excitation of the structure, confirming the behavior exhibited by the eigen-solutions. Throughout this work, it is assumed that the surrounding dielectric medium is air ($\epsilon_r = 1$), whereas the metallic parts are made of copper with a thickness of $17 \mu\text{m}$ and conductivity $\sigma = 5.88 \cdot 10^7$ S/m.

A. Eigenmode Analysis

The dispersion diagram of the composite EC-SRR/ metallic cylinder periodic medium is presented in Fig. 6. It is easily observed that this diagram is the union of the dispersion diagrams corresponding to the two separate media in Figs. 2 and 4. More specifically, the branch corresponding to the fundamental mode of the EC-SRR is present and almost identical to the one of separate EC-SRR medium, whereas the branch which corresponds to the metallic cylinders' supported mode is returned, invariant with respect to the one exhibited by the cylinder composite medium alone. Interestingly, the lightline mode returned by the separate EC-SRR medium

Fig. 7. Field distributions of the modes supported by the combined EC-SRR/metallic cylinder medium at 4 GHz. Normal electric field distribution (E_z) of the cylinder mode (left) and the EC-SRR mode (right). The field distributions are unaffected compared to the ones returned by the solution of the separate simulated media.

Fig. 8. Excitation results for the combined EC-SRR/metallic cylinder medium. The minimization of transmission at the frequency zone by the corresponding dispersion diagram (Fig. 6) remains almost unaffected for all angles simulated. The incidence at $\theta = 90^\circ$ exhibits full reflection due to the response of the metallic cylinders.

vanishes, due to the presence of the cylinders' mode at this wave polarization ($E_z, -H_y, k_x$). It is concluded that the proposed periodic structure is capable of supporting both electromagnetic modes, each of which is excited by a discrete wave polarization: A (E_y, H_z, k_x) polarized impinging wave excites the EC-SRR mode, whereas a ($E_z, -H_y, k_x$) wave excites the metallic cylinders' mode. The field distributions of each mode illustrated in Fig. 7 confirm the aforementioned statements: They are identical to the field distributions supported by each medium separately, therefore the presence of each component does not alter the properties of the other one at all.

B. Plane Wave Excitation

Here, we present the results of the excitation of the structure under study, under the incidence of a plane wave. The angle of electric field polarization varies from $\theta = 0^\circ$ to $\theta = 90^\circ$. In Fig. 8 the returned transmission coefficients are depicted. Interestingly, the minimization of transmission remains almost unaffected for greater angles compared to the separate EC-SRR case, whereas the incidence at 90° now results to full reflection ($S_{21} = 0$), due to the presence of the metallic cylinder.

Fig. 9. (a) Unit cell of a composite medium consisting of a complementary EC-SRR placed at a distance of d_{pcb_2} above an EC-SRR particle (b) Unit cell of a microstrip-terminated EC-SRR particle (c) Unit cell of the proposed polarization-independent SRR (PI-SRR). A microstrip-grounded simplified complementary EC-SRR is placed above an EC-SRR particle at a distance of d_{pcb_2} .

III. A FULLY PLANAR STRUCTURE

We now proceed to the conversion of the proposed composite particle to a fully planar structure. For this purpose, the metallic cylinders need to be substituted by a planar particle, the 3d-periodic repetition of which forms a composite medium exhibiting negative effective permittivity. According to the literature, the Complementary Split-Ring Resonator (C-SRR) is the particle which possesses the dual properties of the SRR, considering in-plane incidence: Electric resonance is created when an incident electric field impinges on such a medium, polarized normally to the scatterers' plane, resulting to the creation of antiparallel electric polarizability [31]–[34]. As thoroughly described in [37], [48], there are many variations of the design of the initially proposed complementary particle, which maintain the basic property of supporting its fundamental electrically resonant mode, provided that the complementary particles are fully or partially terminated at a metallic ground plane. For example, the partial ground termination of microstrip-grounded and cross-grounded complementary SRRs, or the simplified complementary EC-SRR comprise of media with equivalent behavior with the initially proposed design. It is noted that all the described designs of the complementary SRR particles are of resonant type, exhibiting a negative effective permittivity medium property at a specific frequency zone around resonance compared to the more broadband non-resonant response of the medium consisting of metallic cylinders.

Our first attempt is the substitution of the cylinder with the standard complementary EC-SRR particle, which is placed above the ordinary SRR particle at a fixed distance, resulting to the structure depicted in Fig. 9(a). The dispersion diagram of this structure, under the assumption of k_x wave incidence is given in Fig. 10. It is observed that, in this medium, the only supported modes are the ones caused by the presence of the complementary SRR particle (a typical dispersion curve of a resonant medium), whereas the ordinary SRR particle contribution is “masked” (hidden) by the presence of the complementary EC-SRR (its dispersion curve exhibits a totally evanescent field). The former finding is confirmed by the plot of the corresponding field distributions of the supported modes and the wave propagation problem solutions (not shown). Therefore, we conclude that a direct placement

Fig. 10. Dispersion diagram corresponding to the composite medium of Fig. 9(a) for k_x incidence. The medium supports only the complementary EC-SRR modes (blue color), whereas the SRR modes turn evanescent (red color).

of the complementary EC-SRR particle on a certain distance above (or below, as also confirmed by the simulation) an ordinary SRR particle, as a substitute to the metallic cylinder particle, does not result to a fully planar medium which supports the superposition of the modes of its individual components. It is noted that the distance between the particles does not play any significant role relatively to the appearance or not of the SRR mode, as also proved by the corresponding simulations. Therefore, our next step is to reveal the reason for this screening of the SRR mode.

Taking into account the aforementioned analysis, we choose to simulate a separate EC-SRR particle terminated on a ground plane, fully or partially, in order to assess its behavior with respect to metal backing. Beginning with the fully metal-backed case, the results returned from the solution of the eigenproblem prove that this structure does not support a resonant mode, as this is destroyed by the presence of the ground plane. Subsequently, an EC-SRR particle terminated at cross-shaped microstrip pattern is simulated, with identical results: The behavior of this medium remains invariant with respect to the fully-grounded case, as the SRR mode is destroyed, as well. We may conclude that the disappearance of the SRR mode is due to the existence of the metal-backing, either full or placed with a specific pattern (e.g. a cross in the last simulation), but in all cases allowing the electrical connection between the unit cells at xy plane, at both directions (x and y). In this way, the resonant magnetic mode supported by a split-ring particle is destroyed resulting to the destruction of the induced magnetic polarizability α_{zz} exhibited by the EC-SRR effective medium.

We now choose to maintain the partial conductive connection only at the direction of propagation (k_x). The simulation results of a microstrip-terminated EC-SRR medium (Fig. 9(b)) are illustrated in Fig. 11, with the microstrip width w_m varying from 8 mm to 1 mm. We may observe that the resonance is now visible, as the current medium allows the existence of the SRR mode, also confirmed by the field distributions above the resonators' surface, which are identical to the non-metal backed case. A reduction in microstrip width results in the reduction of the resonance frequency of the medium and a slight increase in the bandgap's bandwidth. We may conclude that, in order for the SRR mode to be supported, a partial metal termination is needed at the direction of propagation (k_x

Fig. 11. Dispersion diagram of a microstrip-grounded EC-SRR composite medium (Fig.9(b)). The EC-SRR mode is supported by the medium. Reduction in microstrip width reduces the position of the bandgap in frequency, while it slightly increases its bandwidth.

Fig. 12. Dispersion diagrams of the PI-SRR composite medium configuration illustrated in Fig.9(c) for k_x incidence with $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm (a) and $d_{pcb} = 1.2$ mm (b). The medium supports both the EC-SRR mode and the complementary EC-SRR mode.

Fig. 13. Dispersion diagrams of the PI-SRR composite medium configuration illustrated in Fig.9(c) for k_x incidence with $d_{pcb} = 0.8$ mm (a) and $d_{pcb} = 0.4$ mm (b). The medium supports both the EC-SRR mode and the complementary EC-SRR mode.

in this case), allowing the effective magnetic polarizability to be formed. Thus, as a constraint for our synthesis process, for the purpose of the appearance of the SRR magnetic resonant mode, the electrical disconnection of the metal backing pattern is absolutely necessary, at least at one direction.

Proposed in [48], a novel design of a complementary EC-SRR particle is the simplified complementary EC-SRR particle, illustrated in Fig. 9(c). Assuming k_x incidence, this particle retains the property of supporting the fundamental mode of the classical complementary EC-SRR particle. In

Fig. 14. Transmission coefficients returned by the excitation of the PI-SRR composite medium configuration illustrated in Fig.9(c) with $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm and $d_{pcb} = 1.2$ mm at $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = \pi/2$.

Fig. 15. Transmission coefficients returned by the excitation of the PI-SRR composite medium configuration illustrated in Fig.9(c) with $d_{pcb} = 0.8$ mm and $d_{pcb} = 0.4$ mm at $\theta = 0$ and $\theta = \pi/2$.

addition, it is obvious that it allows an electrical connection at the propagation direction, crucial for the appearance of the aforementioned mode, whereas it also permits the disconnection at the y -direction, enabling the support of an SRR mode simultaneously, if combined with an ordinary EC-SRR particle. Therefore, returning to our initial configuration, we now combine the microstrip-terminated simplified complementary EC-SRR particle with the ordinary EC-SRR particle and assess the behavior of this composite via an eigen-simulation. As illustrated in Figs. 12 and 13, both modes are now supported by this medium, forming two discrete branches visible on the dispersion diagrams. Furthermore, a parametric simulation is performed, with the variation of the distance separating the resonators taken into account (we assume an equal distance between the resonators $d_{pcb_1} = d_{pcb_2} = d_{pcb}$). It is observed that for distances between 1.6 mm and 0.8 mm the discrete modes exhibit a behavior where both bandgap regions (due to electric and magnetic resonance) lay at the same frequency zone. In addition, the excitation simulations of the aforementioned medium are performed. In Figs. 14 and 15 the transmission coefficients for a varying d_{pcb} parameter are presented. We may observe the confirmation of the dispersion diagrams of Figs. 12 and 13, where the transmission minima agree with the corresponding bandgaps. Finally, in Fig. 16, the field distributions of the supported modes at 5 GHz are illustrated (evaluated by the solution of the eigenproblem), at planes just above the surfaces of the particles. The existence of both SRR and complementary SRR modes is easily distinguishable, with the two modes maintaining their separate characteristics. After the presented analysis, the proposed particle may be named as the polarization-independent splitting resonator (PI-SRR) for in-plane wave incidence.

IV. THE UNIPLANAR PI-SRR COMPOSITE MEDIUM

In this last section we propose a novel fully-planar structure which incorporates both an SRR and a complementary SRR particle on the same plane, with a capability to support their modes simultaneously. The unit cell of the structure - illustrated in Fig. 17 - consists of a complementary EC-SRR surrounded by a single-split SRR, whereas there is a partial termination of the unit cell at a microstrip of width w_m .

Fig. 16. Field distributions for the PI-SRR medium just above the scatterers' plane at 5 GHz. Normal electric field component (E_z) on the EC-SRR component (left) and normal magnetic field component (H_z) on the simplified complementary EC-SRR component (right). It is observed that the proposed combined particle maintains both the modes of its separate components almost intact.

Fig. 17. The proposed uniplanar version of the PI-SRR particle. The simplified complementary EC-SRR remains is surrounded by an one-ring EC-SRR. The geometric parameters are: $d_x = d_y = d_z = 13$ mm, $r = 3.6$ mm, $w = 0.9$ mm, $s = 0.2$ mm, $t = 0.2$ mm, $d_{pcb} = 1.6$ mm, $d_m = 1$ mm, $w_0 = 0.45$ mm, $s_0 = 2$ mm and $t_0 = 0.15$ mm.

It is observed that this design satisfies all the design criteria, as discussed thoroughly in the previous sections: A single-split SRR is utilised as the μ_r -negative particle, whereas a com-

Fig. 18. (a) Dispersion diagram of the uniplanar PI-SRR (Fig. 17. The SRR mode and the complementary SRR mode are supported by the medium. (b) Excitation results. The returned transmission coefficients are in perfect agreement with the dispersion diagram.

Fig. 19. Field distributions for the uniplanar PI-SRR medium (Fig.17) just above the scatterers' plane at 5 GHz. Normal electric field component (E_x) (left) and normal magnetic field component (H_z) (right). It is observed that the proposed particle is capable of supporting both modes of its separate components.

plementary EC-SRR is the ϵ_r -negative particle. In addition, there is an electrical connection between the unit cells and the proposed particle is partially terminated by a microstrip at a distance of d_{pcb} . Of course, a question arises as to the degree to which the two particles couple with each other, since they are printed on the same substrate. But this is an issue that is resolved by observing the dispersion diagrams and the field distributions of the supported modes.

In the left subfigure of Fig. 18, the dispersion diagram of the proposed composite particle is depicted. It is easily observed that two distinct modes are supported by the proposed 3-d periodic composite medium, one related to the complementary EC-SRR particle and the other exhibited by the surrounding one-ring EC-SRR particle. The field distributions of these modes are illustrated in Fig. 19 at 5 GHz, where it is seen that each mode corresponds exclusively to a separate particle, justifying the successful design of this novel combined particle, which seems to possess the capability of supporting both modes, almost unaffected by one another. Finally, the excitation results of these media are shown in Fig. 18(b). We may observe a perfect agreement between the transmission minima and the corresponding bandgaps on the dispersion diagram of Fig. 18(a).

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we propose a novel metamaterial composite exhibiting simultaneous electric and magnetic resonance in the same direction at a microwave frequency zone. Utilizing a fully computational approach, we begin by studying the combination of an EC-SRR with a metallic cylinder vertically placed at its center, producing a particle capable of supporting independently both the modes of its constituting particles, when assigned in a periodic lattice. Subsequently, the substitution of the cylinder with the recently proposed

simplified complementary EC-SRR results in the fully planar version of the metamaterial particle. The eigen-simulation results prove its capability of superimposing the modes of its separate particles simultaneously, whereas the excitation results depict its ability to screen the electromagnetic wave under both polarization incidences. Therefore it is rightly assigned the title of Polarization-Independent SRR (PI-SRR). As a last step, we propose the uniplanar version of this particle by printing both an ordinary SRR and a complementary EC-SRR on the same plane. The exhibited dispersions diagrams along with the field distributions of the supported electric and magnetic modes confirm its unique properties.

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